

Mirjam Krause, Anita Thaler, Katharina Santer, Sandra Karner, Christina Seliger & David Steinwender

Sowing change: A women*'s garden as queer-feminist intervention in biodiversity research

David, Miri, Sandra, Chrissi, Kathi and Anita with Edith Zitz, Wolfgang Kogler and Andreas Motschiunig, who supported the women*'s garden (see acknowledgements).

Mirjam Krause studied psychology and has experience in social pedagogy, she works at FUG (Forum Urbanes Gärtnern) in Graz and is responsible for the supervision and support of community gardens.

Anita Thaler is a senior researcher at IFZ (Interdisciplinary Research Centre for Technology, Work and Culture), heads the research area Gender, Science & Technology and the working group Queer STS. She began as a guerrilla gardener at age 7, her passion is landscape gardening, creating multispecies meeting spaces.

Katharina Santer is a social educator and employee in the FUG in winter and a shepherdess in summer. Gardening is her passion since many years, she created several gardens for exploring and growing her own vegetables and she would like to have a huge garden in the future to provide herself and her environment with good food.

Sandra Karner is a senior researcher at IFZ and heads the research unit on Sustainable Food Systems. She loves spending time outdoors in nature and is a passionate gardener who grows various vegetables and fruits in her garden.

Christina Seliger is part of FUG and a Global Studies Master student at University of Graz. She has been involved in various garden projects, focusing more and more on facilitating group processes and educational aspects.

David Steinwender is a researcher at IFZ and part of the research unit on Sustainable Food Systems. He has been involved in urban community gardening projects and supports these initiatives for almost 15 years.

Introduction

“I was not speaking of a marginality one wishes to lose – to give up or surrender as part of moving into the center – but rather of a site one stays in, clings to even, because it nourished one’s capacity to resist. It offers to one the possibility of radical perspective from which to see and create, to imagine alternatives, new worlds.” bell hooks (1990, p. 150)

Fence post by fence post, seed by seed, we have created a garden over the last few months. It was built by many hands. It has been created from many ideas.

A garden in which vegetables have already been harvested and in which there is an attempt to free ourselves from existing patriarchal power structures and hierarchies that exist out there and to surpass them. We heed the call of bell hooks (1990) and see our garden as a „possibility of a radical perspective from which one can see and create, imagine alternatives, new worlds.“¹

Photo of a summer lilac, a neophyte, which bloomed in our garden²

After months of gardening together, on 21 June, we come together to celebrate the solstice. Solstice is a festival where people come together and the longest day is celebrated. We celebrate the fact that we can be here together and have created this place together.

It is a place by and for women*³.

Why it needs a garden by and for women*

Women* are forced to submit to the clutches of the patriarchal system over and over again. Ideas and stigmas about how women* should be and act still characterize our society today. These ideas and expectations manifest in tangible inequality. Women* in Austria face a significantly higher risk of being affected by poverty (Statistik Austria 2023⁴) and access to opportunities for co-determination and actively participate in societal decision-making is more difficult (Hansen 2024). We want to change this a little with the garden.

1 Our introduction, parts of “Why it needs a garden by and for women*” and “A women*’s garden as queer-feminist intervention” were previously published in a blog post by Mirjam Krause: <https://urbanegaertnern.at/allgemein/2024/06/27/sonnwend-garteln/>

2 All photos in this contribution were taken by the authors, depicted persons were asked for their consent to publish the photos.

3 We understand the word women* as being inclusive for all people (sometimes) identifying as women. We don’t want to hold on to the binary system but as for many garden participants the queer approach of a non-binary gender system is quite new and not applicable to them, so we decided to use this term.

4 “Women aged 18 and over made up the largest population group with 95,000 significantly materially and socially disadvantaged a share of 47 %. In addition, 70,000 men aged 18 and over (35 %) and 36,000 children and young people (18 %) were children and adolescents (18%) were also part of this group affected by absolute poverty” (quote from Statistik Austria 2023, p.1, translated with <https://www.deepl.com>).

Our garden project⁵ is part of a bigger transdisciplinary research project – PLANET4B⁶ – which aims to better understand decisions that can affect biodiversity. PLANET 4B uses the concept of intersectionality to address social injustices in these decision-making processes:

“Intersectionality highlights that race, gender, disability, sexuality, class, age, and other social categories are interrelated and lead to different levels of power and oppression influenced by forces like colonialism and neoliberalism.” (Thaler & Karner 2023, p. 5).

We know from international studies that the main reason for a lack of food security is poverty (Van Breemen 2014; Swinnen 2015). In economically difficult times, households affected by poverty and at risk of poverty often compensate their budget for food in order to be able to afford other necessary expenses, as one affected woman explained in an interview:

“You buy reduced products and not what the children would like or what is healthy. I could no longer decide whether to buy wholemeal or normal pasta, spelt bread or wheat toast. You buy according to price, not quality. This is where nutritional poverty begins.”
(Daniela Brodesser 2024, p. 29⁷).

Women⁸ aged 18 and over are one of the largest population groups of materially and socially disadvantaged people in Austria (Statistics Austria 2023). The highest risk of being affected by absolute poverty⁹ is among single-parent households, women¹⁰ living alone and, in particular, retired women living alone (ibid.). People with a migrant background are also more at risk of poverty or social exclusion than people born in Austria (OECD/European Commission 2023).

5 See more about our transformative research approach with this garden here:

<https://www.ifz.at/en/projekt/planet4b-project-understanding-plural-values-intersectionality-leverage-points-attitudes>

6 PLANET4B (<https://planet4b.eu>) receives funding from the European Union’s Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101082212, from UK Research and Innovation (UKRI) under the UK government’s Horizon Europe funding guarantee and from the Swiss State Secretariat for Education, Research and Innovation (SERI).

7 The originally German quote was translated with deepl.com.

8 The statistics we refer on work within the binary system. Women as a term is used referring to the sex assigned at birth.

9 “A household is considered to be at risk of poverty or exclusion if it is significantly

- materially and socially disadvantaged, i.e. affected by absolute poverty, or has less than 60% of the median
- median income or is only integrated into working life to a limited extent.”
(quote from Statistik Austria 2023, p.2, translated with <https://www.deepl.com>).

10 In the data and reports of Statistics Austria or OECD there are only binary concepts used, so we refer to women here, as they are defined by the quoted reports and sources.

This risk of poverty and social exclusion also directly impacts decisions regarding the food supply of affected families as is known from international studies too:

"By household type, the group of women living alone in households at risk of poverty or exclusion had the lowest expenditure on food at €217.

...

If there are not enough funds left after deducting the monthly fixed costs, people often have to save on food. For 13% of people in households at risk of poverty or exclusion, a balanced diet with a full main course was not affordable (vs. 2.9% in households not at risk) ..."
(Hammer & Skina-Tabue 2022, p. 122)

A South African study has identified sustainably designed edible gardens as an effective strategy for improving food security in low-income areas (Van Breemen 2014), and a systematic review concluded that community-based participatory agricultural interventions are indeed promising strategies to reduce food insecurity in developing countries (Doustmohammadian et al. 2022).

These findings on social dimensions of poverty, the connection to food insecurity and sustainable gardens, as well as participatory interventions backed up our transformative biodiversity research project with an intersectionality perspective in Austria, to us it makes sense to us to research this further by co-creating a biodiverse garden as a women*'s space.

We want to bring it into the center of our transformative research¹¹ and knowledge co-creation and it is an attempt to give women* a place where they can be far away from systemic oppression or others. Where the patriarchal approach of competition and performance and doing for others no longer count, but women*-gardeners take the center stage of their own co-creation.

Phase 1 (March 8th – April 5th) – Building a group and planning a garden

When we come together, we come together as a community on Fridays, trying to meet each other with goodwill and seeing each other.

It all started on 8 March 2024. The day on which the oppression of FLINTA* (women, lesbians, intersex, non-binary, trans, agender) people is highlighted and denounced. For us, 8 March was a day when a group of women* came together to build a place that was theirs*.

The women*s garden – what later will be named as “GAIA Gartenberg” (translated “GAIA garden hill”, because it is a garden planted on a hilly area of Graz) by the wo-

¹¹ The Planet4B project established a transdisciplinary diagnostic framework (Barton 2024) using – beside others – the leverage points and three spheres of transformation approach (Meadows 1999, Sharma 2007,)

men* themselves – is established on the international women’s day in a community centre in Graz¹². It is an information event¹³, a kick-off and also the first of the coming women* only events, giving women* a room to be around other women* (including children of all genders).

Between 10 and 15 women* come in this first phase, each Friday afternoon¹⁴ and are greeted by Miri and Kathi, two gardeners with pedagogical training, who design not only this first and crucial phase of building a group based on the philosophy of a brave space¹⁵ and considering the diversity¹⁶ of the women*, but also co-create the gardening and biodiversity knowledge with the group. Miri and Kathi establish a routine for the group, starting with a checking-in exercise, often an energizer to bring the focus in the here and now and help the women* to pay attention to the group. Then either planning or social activities, later gardening activities are following, interrupted by breaks of sharing homemade food, and at last always an official checking-out takes place to say properly thank you and good bye.

In this group-building phase a first so called ‘research activity’ takes place. The participating women* receive a stamp card to collect stamps whenever they participate in research activities¹⁷:

12 The area in Graz was provided by the city of Graz for this specific purpose of creating an edible garden with members of the local community. The plans to do this garden were communicated with leaflets and an information event at the neighbouring community centre. Leaflets were spread in institutions of the neighbourhood, where vulnerable women* were assumed to visit or be located. Additionally, the community centre helped with reaching out personally and via multipliers.

13 The research team at IFZ and the gardeners of Forum Urbanes Gärtnern (FUG), both facilitators of the Austrian case study) decided – in line with the findings in the literature and the focus on a garden for women* – that only women* of the research team of IFZ would participate occasionally in the group, so Anita and Sandra were part of the kick-off and later research workshops and special events, like the spring festival, David was included in conceptual and reflection meetings outside the women*s’ group. Likewise, also from the FUG gardeners’ team only Mirjam (Miri), Katharina (Kathi) and later Christina (Chrissi) were actively involved in the women*s’ garden activities.

14 The time slot changed a bit as the days grew warmer, but the group always met 3 hours on each Friday regardless of the weather or holidays for the whole garden season. The first phase took place at the community centre nearby the garden, later most Fridays were spent together at the garden, with only exceptions on very rainy days/hours or during special events.

15 More information on creating braver spaces and the meaning behind it on <https://katharina-debus.de/wp-content/uploads/Debus-Saadi-Verletzlichkeit-Bildung-Safer-Braver.pdf>

16 The women are born in different countries in Europe and Asia, their age ranges from teenager to pensioner, some are mothers, they live in the neighbourhood of the garden and have currently no own garden. They speak different languages, so we talk and translate everything in German and English, the women* help themselves with translation apps on their mobiles.

17 Full stamp cards are worth 200 Euro.

Picture of our stamp card, which collects participation stamps, and can be traded for vouchers worth 200 Euros, when full. The vouchers can be used to purchase goods in the local area.

This first research activity is an ‘experience-stroll’ in the garden to be, which in the beginning is an overgrown area of a mostly neglected piece of land owned by the city. While the 14 women* walk in pairs they talk about their personal experiences around gardening and their expectations. From this we learn that those who already have some gardening experiences learned their skills and gardening knowledge mostly from their parents, sometimes mothers are explicitly mentioned, and their grandparents. Some come from farms or even learned agricultural jobs, but that does not mean they automatically knew how to cultivate a garden; sometimes they experienced very hard work but did not experience the pleasure of gardening before. One woman tells us about her upbringing in Mumbai, where gardening is not considered a women’s activity, and so she is initially only accompanying her daughter to the GAIA Gartenberg, who learned all about gardens from ChatGPT and her geography teacher and wholeheartedly wants to be a gardener.

The highlight of this first phase probably is the garden plan, which is co-created based on existing garden knowledge within the group, on handouts and books, and the wishes of the women*: What kind of food would they like to grow and later cook and/or eat? The colourful plan is presented at the spring fest on April 5th, where IFZ researchers Anita and Sandra and also children and female friends and family of the women* are invited, to talk and read about gardening, pricking out plants and bring and share one’s favourite food.

Photo of our seedlings, in the background Kathi talks to participants at our spring festival

Part of the garden plan is a mixed crop bed called ‘Milpa’-bed or ‘the three sisters’¹⁸: corn, beans and pumpkins.

“Being among the sisters provides a visible manifestation of what a community can become when its members understand and share their gifts. In reciprocity, we fill our spirits as well as our bodies.”

(Robin Wall Kimmerer 2013, p. 134)

Phase 2 (April 12th – May 24th) – Sowing seeds and hard labour

Deciding to work as a women*s only group also means that constructing a fence, building a garden shed or digging large holes for shrubs have to be accomplished within this group of women*. In spring between 7 and 12 women* come and experience that doing the hard labour can feel very good, although some of the women* experienced these activities only as ‘men’s work’ in their countries of origin.

In April and May also many seeds and plants are brought to the soil, the co-created garden plan from phase 1 is coming to life. The women* work together, share food, stories, and laughs. Miri and Kathi recognize that although everyone seems to be focused on the garden work, they all very much appreciate the time spent with each other, reflecting on their thoughts, experiences and needs. The women* tell how comfortable they feel in this group, how they like the understanding for each other, how much joy they have in this group, and how much they look forward to their garden Fri-

¹⁸ The Milpa system is originally a Latin American tradition of planting corn to give halt to the winding beans, and using the pumpkins with their big leaves to provide shadow for the roots and reduce the evaporation of water, Robin Wall Kimmerer describes the same approach as Three Sisters stemming from the indigenous people of Northern America.

days. In this phase the name of the garden is more and more a topic of the Fridays, and ideas are collected.

One woman* tells about their personal realisation of their love of manual labour and that they got the opportunity to train as a gardening specialist.

Due to a lack of infrastructure in the garden in these first months, the women*s group has to borrow water from neighbours, and so they connect especially to one neighbour who tells about worries in the neighbourhood whether these GAIA Gartenberg activities mean that there will be drug dealers in the area like it used to be before the overgrown patch was turned into a garden. This tells us that information events (like we did one in March) and sharing information at the community centre (flyers and informing people in person at the centre) are never enough; some neighbours have to be included explicitly, maybe the regular talks while borrowing water could be a good start?

Another lesson in phase 2 is that Miri and Kathi do not have to plan and design all activities and they can trust the process. There are two signs that our transformative approach indeed works. The first incident occurs, when a woman* tells an idea for a herbal garden, a group of women* joins to creatively plan this herbal garden and many women* bring in further ideas. The second occasion is the building of a potato tower, which was brought in as an idea, and later on also implemented by a woman* with gardening experience and the help of others. We realise we do not need to plan everything; we can trust that this group will come up with its own solutions, if we just start the process with the first questions or tasks. The women* are so motivated that Miri and Kathi offer to stay longer, so they officially end the garden Fridays with their check-out ritual, but after that some women* stay and work on their own. However, motivated and self-organised the women* are, some of them do not have a lot of garden work experience and are sometimes not well equipped, so some need guidance on tools and others need rubber boots and rain jackets. Taking nothing for granted and supporting the group in a democratic and non-hierarchical way is a guiding principle, we are all learning along the way.

As a preparation for future research activities, the women* are asked to name their personal favourite vegetable or fruit, and the list comprises tomatoes, zucchini, potatoes, mushrooms, raspberries, apples and mangos. We will cover some of those in research activities, some of them will grow in the garden, and others can only be bought in Austria – this makes visible that people who live far from their country of origin sometimes miss the flavour of their childhood, their comfort food – how can we compensate that?

May 24th – entry in the garden diary “YIPPIEH, our first own radish!”

Photo of a hand holding radish plants with soil on their roots and green leaves

Phase 3 (May 31st – July 26th) – Harvesting vegetables and saying goodbye

The rainy period continues, so Kathi, Miri and the 5-10 women* sometimes meet in the community centre and do indoor activities, like painting signs for the garden, eating together, listening to music and sharing stories. On these occasions, when no regular garden Friday is happening, fewer women* come, and everything seems slowed down; the conversations get deeper and more personal. Women* talk about their lives, their working experiences as carers, and share their stories of suffering and death. Although it seems that not so much has been accomplished for the garden, the social dimension of sharing personal stories is tremendously important.

Although many women* come already exhausted from their full week of work to the garden on Fridays, they leave happy and satisfied; gardening and experiencing the connection within the group seems to have a balancing and almost meditative impact on us all. So even when one woman* breaks a leg, another her arm, they still come, and participate in the activities as well as they can¹⁹.

Two ongoing topics dominate the late spring and then the summer. During the rainy days, but also beyond it is the slugs²⁰, and most women* are very frustrated about the sheer number of slugs they have to collect and remove from their vegetable patches again and again, it feels like today's eternal Sisyphus task. The second topic is tomatoes, which will grow so fast and well during the upcoming weeks that the framework to support the plants has to be rebuilt again and again, another Sisyphus task but way more rewarding.

19 See for instance Howarth et al 2020 on the impact of gardens and gardening on health and well-being.

20 „Slugs feed on leaves of many plants (especially seedlings), ripening fruits and vegetables, and decaying plant matter.” (quote from <https://extension.umn.edu/yard-and-garden-insects/slugs>)

The weather changes in June so the group needs protection from the sun instead of the rain now, a solar sail brings some shade, and the women* decide to meet another hour later to avoid the heat in the middle of the day.

In these weeks the harvesting starts, spinach, mangold, radish, beans and more; weeding is an ongoing task, and more vegetables like lettuce, broccoli and cabbage turnips are planted.

It is time to celebrate midsummer, the women* make wreaths, eat together, tell stories, hang little pieces of papers with wishes on trees, and come up with lots of new ideas for the garden.

Photo from our midsummer „solstice“-festival, two women making wreaths.

Two research activities²¹ take place in this phase too. The first begins with the women’s favourite vegetables and fruits and reflects on regions, diversity and seasonality. The stories about favourite fruits and vegetables are often connected to personal, family-related, social and cultural, sometimes traditional contexts. The value of food and the sadness because of reduced varieties is discussed and further resources, like podcasts, shared.

The second research workshop uses social science issue teachings²² to showcase biodiversity issues around apples. How are we deciding on buying a specific type of apple? What criteria are important to us? Taste, price, ...? How about working conditions of harvesting workers, health or CO2 emissions? What about different harvesting times for different apples? And how some apples are better for pies than others? There is more to apples than we thought: we are telling stories, discussing, planning apple orchards in two groups and enjoy a buffet full with homemade apple dishes.

21 As our garden is a biodiversity research case study for the EU funded PLANET4B project, we – IFZ and FUG plus the women* – do co-create a garden and co-create biodiversity knowledge together with invited experts – the group of women* and we are a learning community, in research terms we conduct an innovation lab (see more: <https://www.ifz.at/en/projekt/planet4b-project-understanding-plural-values-intersectionality-leverage-points-attitudes>).

22 See the approach and guiding principles of our cooperation partner <http://www.naturerlebnispark.at/>.

Photo from one of our research activity, a workshop on biodiversity with Andrea Frantz-Pittner in the 'GAIA Gartenberg' garden

In July, women* can take their growing shares of the harvest home, the first tomatoes and peppers, along sage, chives, zucchini, lettuce, cucumber... And it is time to say goodbye to Kathi, who will spend the next months on an alp to herd goats and make cheese. We will all miss her.

Phase 4 (August 2nd-September 6th) – Growing ideas and tomatoes

Miri and Chrissi are gardening with the women* in the summer and autumn. We sometimes start with a walk through the garden to see what is growing, where weeding is needed, where we should use scythed grass to mulch plants, like our berry bushes. And we recognize that our tomatoes outgrew their supporting constructions again, up in the neighbouring woods, collecting branches and here we go Sisyphus. But we are presented with many tasteful tomatoes, the best ones harvested to take out and save the seeds.

Photo of a basket full with harvested red tomatoes

In this phase we have three further research activities, the first one works with a ‘community mapping’ approach to collect and visualize ideas around the sustainable use of the garden and its surroundings in the upcoming months or years. Whose needs are recognised already and who needs to be better included? How can we increase accessibility and for instance help patients from the hospital nearby to use the garden too? How can this all be financed, can a market garden help with that? And do we need a playground when clearly a wood and nature with all its mysteries is a playground itself?

Before we sow seeds for winter vegetables, we discuss human diversity and position ourselves in the wheel of privileges. Often our self-images differ from what our wheels show us, some categories are not visible others are prominent. How important are power and money? Some are irritated, is society really judging along these categories? We share stories of our backgrounds, we are all very different, aren’t we? The group thinks that the diversity brings them together, connects them, the conversation evolves to gratefulness.

The third research workshop discusses diversity, inclusion and accessibility. Guided by a diversity expert, who starts our discussion with questions, we reflect on the diversity within our group: Where are our cultural roots, which languages do we speak? How do we usually come to the garden? Who will be allowed to vote in the upcoming national elections? We also explore our garden through new lenses: What in our garden refers to power, what to love, what to chaos, and what to sweetness? We learn that accessibility is being able to get into our garden. Diversity is getting invited to our table. Inclusion is having a voice at the table. Belonging is having your voice heard at the table.

The gardening is sometimes frustrating (slugs, rain, heat, tomatoes growing to the sky ...) but always rewarding. Even when you think today was not very successful, you can see at the end of the day, what the group has accomplished, it is the growing share of the harvest at the end of each Friday and it is this deeper feeling of belonging and contentment. The garden is a place where we can strengthen ourselves, we are sharing our homemade food, we are sharing stories, and our harvest. Full of pride we take a picture of the rich and colourful harvest, Miri and Chrissi are leaving, some of the women* stay, the group becomes more and more self-dependent.

A photo of a table full of harvested vegetables from our garden

A women*'s garden as queer-feminist intervention – and now?

From hammering the fence posts into the ground to laying out the beds, from sowing to building trellises – we created it all in our garden.

We are all that! And yet people are astonished when we tell them what we have built, and solely with the hands of women*. This probably shows once again that society is still a long way from breaking down the binary gender system and its stigmas.

All the more reason why such places of queer-feminist solidarity are needed, all the more we need places of resistance – „safe spaces, (...) where we learn to dream again, (...)“ (Daniela Gottschlich 2024).

At the time of writing this article, we are planning our final project-related activities in the garden, which includes a workshop, where we systematize our experiences, and analyse the success of our co-creation efforts. The garden and its harvest are obvious and measurable successes, the women* of our innovation lab learned to produce sustainable and healthy food in their garden, and the vegetables provided for them and their partners, families, friends. To better understand the transformative nature of this experience, we will analyse in more detail, besides food, gardening skills and biodiversity knowledge gained at GAIA Gartenberg but also the friendships that developed, along with the growth of self-efficacy and self-determination among participants. The effects on the neighborhood and other potential outcomes will be discussed in the upcoming months and published in the context of PLANET4B.

The garden project at GAIA Gartenberg in Graz has been an innovative experiment on multiple levels, particularly with its intersectional approach focusing on women*. Our goal was to create a garden that not only enhances edible and biodiverse urban green spaces but also actively involves the neighbourhood. The city of Graz has already committed to providing financial resources to expand this green space into an edible park. Plans are currently underway for the planting of fruit trees and berry bushes in the coming months. Ultimately, we hope that GAIA Gartenberg will serve as a model, inspiring the development of the city's food, agriculture, and biodiversity strategies concerning participatory planning including economically disadvantaged citizen groups.

We envision this garden as a local, sustainable source of healthy food, fostering a connection to nature and community education based on co-creative knowledge generation for transformative change.

Acknowledgements: We want to gratefully thank the women* of GAIA Gartenberg for co-creating this wonderful garden and biodiversity knowledge together, our colleagues Andreas Flach and Andreas Motschiunig for their valuable help in 'preparing the ground' (in various respects) for the garden, and Wolfgang Kogler and Anna Reupichler for establishing connections to the neighbourhood community. A special thank you goes to Edith Zitz, Andrea Frantz-Pittner and Reni Hofmüller, who supported us with their advice and organised research workshops with and for our women*'s garden. Finally, we want to thank Maria Nievoll, who endorses the garden development as contact person from the city of Graz.

References

- Barton, David N.; Zolyomi, Agnes; Franklin, Alex; Aas-Hanssen, Alexander Engen; Motschiunig, Andreas; Thaler, Anita; Smith, Barbara; Junker-Köhler, Berit; Loučková, Blanka; Lipka, Borbála; Inoue, Cristina Y. A., Steinwender, David; Simsek, Elif Tugba; Kelemen, Eszter; Ludhra, Geeta; Brown, Geraldine; Sabir, Ghezal; Pataki, György; Figari, Helene; Soliev, Ilkhom; Czett, Kármén; Tenhardt, Lina; Bonetti, Marta; Bykova, Maryna; Ofori-Amanfo, Patricia; Navarro-Gambín, Pedro; Chudy, Rafal; Home, Robert; Karner, Sandra; Vaňo, Simeon; Ludhra, Subash; Gundersen, Vegard; Mendes, Vinícius; Bredin, Yennie K. (2024). Transdisciplinary diagnostic framework for biodiversity decision-making assessment. (Report No D1.7). Project 101082212 – PLANET4B. Brussels: European Research Executive Agency. https://planet4b.eu/wp-content/uploads/2024/05/PLANET4B_D1.7_Transdisciplinary_diagnostic_framework.pdf
- BMGF (2017). Gesundheitsziele Österreich. Richtungsweisende Vorschläge für ein gesünderes Österreich. Langfassung. Aufl. Ausgabe 2017 mit aktualisiertem Vorwort. Bundesministerium für Gesundheit und Frauen, Wien https://gesundheitsziele-oesterreich.at/website2017/wp-content/uploads/2018/08/gz_langfassung_2018.pdf
- Brodesser, Daniela (2024). Angst vor dem Einkauf. In: Anschläge. Das feministische Magazin, V, 2024, p.29.

- Doustmohammadian, Azam, Mohammadi-Nasrabadi, Fatemeh, Keshavarz-Mohammadi, Nastaran, Hajjar, Melika, Alibeyk, Sepideh, & Hajigholam-Saryazdi, Maryam (2022). Community-based participatory interventions to improve food security: A systematic review. *Frontiers in nutrition*, 9, 1028394.
- Hammer, Angela; Skina-Tabue, Magdalena (2022). Konsumstrukturen in armuts- oder ausgrenzunggefährdeten Haushalten. In: *Statistische Nachrichten 2/2022*. Statistik Austria: https://www.statistik.at/fileadmin/pages/338/StN2022_02_Soziales_Armut_Konsum.pdf
- Hansen, Lina & Gerner, Nadine. *Ökofeminismus zwischen Theorie und Praxis: Eine Einführung*. 1. Auflage, 2024. UNRAST-Verlag.
- hooks, bell (1990). Choosing the margin as a space of radical openness. *Yearning: Race, gender, and cultural politics*, p. 150. South End Press.
- Howarth, Michelle; Brettell, Allison; Hardman, Michael; Maden, Michelle (2020). What is the evidence for the impact of gardens and gardening on health and well-being: a scoping review and evidence-based logic model to guide healthcare strategy decision making on the use of gardening approaches as a social prescription. *BMJ Open*. 2020 Jul 19;10(7):e036923. doi: 10.1136/bmjopen-2020-036923. PMID: 32690529; PMCID: PMC7371129.
- Meadows, Donella H. (1999). Leverage points: Places to intervene in a system. The Sustainability Institute. <http://donellameadows.org/archives/leverage-points-places-to-intervene-in-a-system/>
- OECD/European Commission (2023). Indikatoren der Integration von Zugewanderten 2023: Settling In. Paris: OECD Publishing. <https://doi.org/10.1787/13226de3-de>.
- Sharma, Monica (2007). Personal to Planetary Transformation. *Kosmos*, 31–35.
- Statistik Austria (2023). „2022 waren 2,3 % der Bevölkerung erheblich materiell und sozial benachteiligt“. Pressemitteilung 13 049-077/23. <https://www.statistik.at/fileadmin/announcement/2023/04/20230420Armut2022.pdf>
- Swinnen, Johan (2015). Inequality, not unavailability, is the main driver of food insecurity. Interview in: *Horizon. The EU Research & Innovation Magazine*. <https://projects.research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/en/horizon-magazine/inequality-not-unavailability-main-driver-food-insecurity-prof-johan-swinnen>
- Thaler, Anita & Karner, Sandra (eds.) (2023). Methodological framework for intersectionality analysis. (Report No D1.3). Project 101082212 — PLANET4B. Brussels: European Research Executive Agency. <https://planet4b.eu/project-documents/methodological-framework-for-intersectionality-analysis/>
- Van Breemen, Hayley (2014). Cape Town's urban food security plan: a conceptual framework for achieving an accessible and healthy urban food system. <https://open.uct.ac.za/server/api/core/bitstreams/c43971d7-4bc8-4965-8dc7-3b381aeff8ad/content>
- Wall Kimmerer, Robin (2013). *Braiding Sweetgrass. Indigenous Wisdom, Scientific Knowledge and the Teaching of Plants*. Minneapolis: Milkweed Editions.